

Isometric and bacilliform particles of rice tungro virus complex.

The presumed tungro complex particles were isometric and bacilliform (see figure). The isometric particles were 27-28 nm in diameter when negatively stained in 2% uranyl acetate (UA) and 30 nm in diameter in 1% neutral sodium phosphotungstate (PTA). The bacilliform particles were 23 nm in diameter in UA and 31-33 nm in diameter in PTA. The length of the bacilliform particles was variable in both stains. Apparently undamaged particles with both ends rounded were 110-190 nm long in UA, although no particular modal length was detected.

Hibino and associates reported in *Phytopathology* 68:1412, 1978, on the negatively stained appearance and dimensions of particles of the tungro complex. They used PTA only on crude preparations. Our results in PTA confirm their measurements of particles in the same stain. However, we note that the bacilliform particles particularly appeared damaged in our PTA preparations. We think that the substantially greater diameter compared to that in UA was due to artifactual swelling or flattening. ■

second. When nonviruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of both species, none of the progeny became infective.

These results indicate that *N. virescens* is also a vector of RDV, transmitting the virus in a persistent manner with transovarial passage. ■

Survey of rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta from 1978 to 1980

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Rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta were surveyed from 1978 to 1980, with 69 cooperators of the PPD, faculty of Agriculture, University of Can Tho. The results showed 25 diseases in rice fields and 6 fungi on stored grain. Blast, sheath blight, bacterial blight, and ufra were the most important diseases (see table).

Blast and sheath blight appeared everywhere in the delta, but were most severe in three regions.

Blast was severe in Tiengiang region and the southern part of Haugiang region (Fig. 1). In Tiengiang, blast was important in January, February, March, and July, with highest peaks in January and July every year. Node blast occurred in March.

In the southern part of Haugiang province, node blast was common in December-January, and leaf blast, in July. An epidemic of leaf blast in July 1978 destroyed more than 300 ha of seedling nurseries in the main season crop.

Severe sheath blight occurrence was observed in two regions — the northwestern region of the delta encompassing the whole of Angiang province and the northern part of Haugiang province, and in Tiengiang regions (Fig. 2).

Bacterial blight and ufra diseases were important in the rainy season and in deepwater areas. They sometimes caused severe losses in some limited areas.

Kernel smut broke out from February to April 1979 as an epidemic in the northwestern part of the delta. More

A new insect vector of rice dwarf virus

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Rice dwarf virus (RDV) is transmitted in a persistent manner with transovarial passage by *Nephotettix cincticeps*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*.

N. virescens and *N. cincticeps* were collected 1974-1977 from rice fields in Fujian. Infectivity was tested on variety Zhin Zhuai 11 at the 3-leaf stage. Of 988 *N. virescens* and 969 *N. cincticeps* tested, 4.3% and 4.9% of the insects, respectively, were capable of causing

RDV infection in rice plants, indicating that infective insects of both species exist under natural conditions.

After an acquisition feeding of 3-4 days and a latent period of about 9 days both species transmitted the RDV (see table). RDV was persistent in the insect vector.

There was transovarial passage of RDV in both species. When viruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of *N. virescens*, the progeny became infective at 8% for the first generation and 4% for the second. When viruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of *N. cincticeps*, the progeny became infective at 19% for the first generation and 12% for the

Transmission of rice dwarf virus by two species of *Nephotettix*, Shaxian, China.

Species	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (%)	Latent period (days)			
			In insect		In plant	
			Av	Range	Av	Range
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	544	35	9.4	6-32	10.6	7-48
<i>N. virescens</i>	567	31	9.0	7-21	12.4	8-38

Diseases in rice fields in the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 1978 to 1980.^a

Disease	Causal agent	Important notes
Blast	<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i>	+++
Sheath blight	<i>Thanatephorus cucumeris</i>	+++
Bacterial blight	<i>Xanthomonas oryzae</i>	+++
Ufra	<i>Ditylenchus angustus</i>	+++
Rice ragged stunt	Virus, vector <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	+++ → ±
Brown spot	<i>Cochliobolus miyabeanus</i>	++
Kernel smut	<i>Tilletia barclayana</i>	+++ → ±
Bakanae	<i>Gibberella fujikuroi</i>	++ → ±
Bacterial leaf streak	<i>X. translucens</i> var. <i>oryzicola</i>	++ → ±
Narrow brown leaf spot	<i>Sphaerulina oryzae</i>	+
Akagare type II	H ₂ S toxicity	+
Root knot nematode	<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp.	+
Leaf spot	<i>Curvularia lunata</i>	±
Acid sulfate soil toxicity	Fe, Al toxicity, and P deficiency	+
False smut	<i>Ustilagoideia virens</i>	±
Sheath rot	<i>Acrocyndrium oryzae</i>	±
Stem rot	<i>Helminthosporium sigmoideum</i>	±
Stem rot	<i>H. sigmoideum</i> var. <i>irregularare</i>	±
Minute leaf spot	<i>Nigrospora oryzae</i>	±
Stackburn disease	<i>Trichoconis padwickii</i>	±
Small leaf blight	<i>Phyllosticta glumarum</i>	±
Leaf smut	<i>Entyloma oryzae</i>	±
Sheath blotch	<i>Pyrenochaeta oryzae</i>	±
Seedling blight	<i>Botryobasidium rolfsii</i>	±
Bacterial sheath rot	<i>Pseudomonas oryzicola</i>	±
Grassy stunt	Mycoplasma (?)	±
Rice stripe (?)	(?)	±
Orange leaf (?)	(?)	±

^a± light, + medium, ++ heavy, +++ severe, (?) not yet determined.

than 10% diseased grain was observed in some fields in the center of the area.

Rice ragged stunt also broke out severely in 1978 together with the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* epidemic and concentrated in the north-eastern part of the delta.

Bacterial sheath rot (*Pseudomonas*

oryzicola) and seedling blight (*Botryobasidium rolfsii*) were first discovered in the delta in 1978 and 1979.

Fungi on stored grain were *Penicillium* sp., *Aspergillus* sp., *Trichoconis padwickii*, *Gibberella fujikuroi*, *Helminthosporium oryzae*, and *Curvularia lunata*. ■

1. Distribution of regions with severe rice blast the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 1978-80.

2. Distribution of regions with severe sheath blight in the Vietnamese Mekong delta, 1978-80.

Variability in the incidence of udbatta disease on paddy rice varieties in Karnataka State, India, 1978-80

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Udbatta disease (caused by *Ephelis oryzae*) has occurred in Karnataka State for a long time. A fairly high incidence was noticed recently on some high-yielding varieties of paddy rice. In a diseased plant, the entire panicle is infected and incidence in even a single panicle results in 100% loss. This 3-year study was conducted to determine disease incidence in 20 selected paddy rice cultures.

Incidence of udbatta disease in 20 selected rice cultures in Karnataka State, India, 1978-80.

The average disease incidence (see figure) among cultures varied from 4% in IET2295 to 22% in IET3626. The

data indicate a narrow range of variability in disease incidence in the varieties, except in IET3626. ■